

MOLECULAR CHARACTERIZATION OF WILD *Heterobranchus longifilis* FROM SOUTH WEST AND NORTH CENTRAL ZONES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Heterobranchus longifilis is a species with high aquaculture potential, yet its production is constrained by a shortage of quality seed. This study assessed the genetic diversity of wild *H. longifilis* from Southwest (SW) (Ekiti state) and North Central (NC) (Niger state) of Nigeria to evaluate their potential for breeding programs. Genomic DNA from ten adult specimens (five each from two zones) was analyzed using four polymorphic microsatellite primers. Results revealed that the effective number of alleles (AE) was 1.44 ± 0.06 in the SW and 1.65 ± 0.04 in the NC population. The mean number of alleles (AN) was 2.00 ± 0.00 for both populations. The observed heterozygosity (H_o) was variable, ranging from 0.21 in SW to 0.50 in NC, indicating a low level of genetic diversity, particularly in the SW population. Significant genetic differentiation was observed between the populations as revealed by the F_{ST} of 0.225. The study therefore suggests that *H. longifilis* strains from North central population possess considerable genetic diversity, while the Southwest strains require urgent conservation intervention.

Keywords: Molecular characterization, Genetic diversity, *Heterobranchus longifilis*, Microsatellites, Breeding program

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Introduction

Heterobranchius longifilis is a commercially important clariids species with significant potentials for aquaculture. It is widely cultivated, especially in Africa due to its resilient physical condition, growth rate, prolific nature and high commercial value (Jimoh et al., 2021). Also, the species exhibits high reproductive capacities under hatchery conditions, and its broodstock performance and fecundity have been reported to support broodstock management (Robert et al., 2024). Despite these aquaculture potentials and desirable biological traits, detailed growth rate data vary with culture systems and diets (Eyo and Ivon, 2017; Yakubu et al., 2014) and production remains low and primarily at the subsistence level (Agbebi, et al., 2013); This is due to insufficient seed supply for stocking, as well as challenges in feed and marketing (Adewumi and Olaleye, 2011). Furthermore, the supply of fingerlings from Nigerian hatcheries, including those for *H. longifilis*, is insufficient to meet demand, thereby highlighting the need for improved broodstock management and selective breeding using improved genetic approaches (FAO, 2007; Adewumi and Olaleye, 2011; Ogedegbe et al., 2016).

Molecular characterization using microsatellite markers (which are highly polymorphic and co-dominant) has proven to be one of the essential approaches for such genetic improvement programs (Ogbueunu and Awodiran, 2017), as they are widely used to evaluate genetic variation, population structure, and relationships within and between fish population (Wenne, 2023; Kumar, 2019). Therefore, this study characterized the genetic diversity of wild *H. longifilis* from Southwest (SW) (Ekiti state) and North-Central (NC) (Niger state) Nigeria using microsatellite markers. The study aims to

provide preliminary data essential towards domestication of these strains and support the enhancement of breeding programs and the availability of *H. longifilis* seed stock.

Materials and Methods

Study Area:

This study was carried out in the Fish Genetics and Biotechnology Department, National Institute for Freshwater Fisheries Research, New-Bussa, Niger state.

Sample Collection:

Ten *H. longifilis* broodstock (five each from the two zones) were obtained with the help of commercial fishermen from the tropical environment in Egbe reservoir, Gbonyin Local Government Area of Ekiti State, Southwestern Nigeria, and the Guinea Savannah environment in Karabonde - Kanji lake, Borgu Local Government Area of Niger state. Pectoral fin clips were cut from the fish samples and preserved in 10% ethanol.

Isolation of DNA:

DNA was extracted from 0.03 g of *H. longifilis* pectoral fin tissue using Geneaid Biotech Ltd gSYNC™ DNA Extraction Kit (Taiwan), following the protocol described by Galbusera et al. (1996). The concentration and purity of the DNA samples were assessed using a nanodrop spectrophotometer (Nanodrop® ND-1000, Thermo Fisher Scientific India Pvt. Ltd) at 260/280 nm.

Primer Optimization:

Primers (Cga01, Cga02, Cga03, and Cga05 originally developed in African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) and characterized by Galbusera et al., (1996) were optimized. A reaction mix was prepared with Master-Mix (DNA polymerase, 5 x reaction buffer (0.4 M Tris

HCL, 0.1 (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.1% w/v Tween-20), 12.5 mM MgCl₂ (1 x PCR Solution – 2.5 mM MgCl₂), 1mM deoxyribose nucleotide triphosphate (1 x PCR solution -200 μM dATP, 200 μM dCTP, 200 μM dGTP, 200 μM dTTP), paired primers, and nuclease-free water (FIREPol® Master Mix, Solis BioDyne, Estonia). A gradient PCR which consisted of a pre-denaturation at 95 °C for 5 min, followed by 35 cycles of denaturation (95 °C for 30 s), primer-specific annealing

temperature (T_m) for 30 s, extension (72 °C for 30 s), and a final extension at 72 °C for 10 min was performed. The annealing temperature (T_m) was 51 °C, 50 °C, 48 °C and 55 °C for Cga01, Cga02, Cga03, and Cga05 respectively (Table 1). The primers were used to amplify their respective minisatellite regions using a Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) in a thermocycler (GeneAmp® PCR System 9700, Applied Biosystems, Thermo Fisher Scientific India Pvt. Ltd).

Table 1: Primer Sequence

Locus	Array	Primer sequence (5'- 3' and 3'-5')	Annealing temperature (°C)
Cga01	(GT)15	GGCTAAAAGAACCCTGTCTG TACAGCGTCGATAAGCCAGG	51
Cga02	(GT)10N2(GT)8	GCTAGTGTGAACGCAAGGC ACCTCTGAGATAAAACACAGC	50
Cga03	(GT)21	CACTTCTTACATTTGTGCCC ACCTGTATTGATTTCTTGCC	48
Cga05	(GT)11N2(GT)2	TCCACATTAAGGACAACCACCG TTTGCAGTTCACGACTGCCG	55

Gel Electrophoresis and Scoring:

5 μl PCR products were run on a 2% agarose gel stained with ethidium bromide. 2 g of agarose powder was measured into a beaker and 100 ml of 1 X TAE (Tris-Acetate-EDTA) buffer was added. The mixture was incubated in an oven for 2 min to enable it dissolve. Afterwards, the solution was allowed to cool (60 °C), and 5 μl of ethidium bromide was added to the solution and properly mixed. The gel was poured into a tray containing combs and left to set for 35 min. The gel was placed in the electrophoresis tank (BIO-RAD®, USA), 1X TAE (Tris-Acetate-EDTA) buffer was added, and electrophoresis was performed at 100 V

for 45 min. The gel was then visualized under UV light.

Statistical Analysis:

Gel bands were transformed into binary data using GelQuest (2008). The resulting data were analyzed using GenAIEx 6.502 (Peakall and Smouse, 2006; Peakall and Smouse, 2012). Genetic structure was assessed by estimating the inbreeding coefficients (FIS, FIT) and the fixation index (FST) using Wright's F-statistics (Wright, 1951).

Results

Concentration and Purity: Quality and purity were determined by absorbance ratio at 260/280 nm. Concentrations were between the range of 33.4 ng/ μ l (NC F2) to 378.09 ng/ μ l (NC M3) (Table 2). Similarly, all Samples

from Southwest (Ekiti) and Northcentral (Niger) showed good DNA purity, with 260/280 nm ratios between 1.89 and 2.06 (Table 2), indicating minimal protein contamination.

Table 2: Concentration and Purity of DNA

S/N	Sample ID	Concentration (ng/ μ l)	Purity (260/280 nm)
1	SW F1	263.83	1.94
2	NC M2	160.63	1.94
3	NCM1	169.14	1.89
4	SW F2	198.4	1.92
5	SW M1	163.94	1.95
6	SW M2	110.19	2.06
7	NCF1	92.93	1.91
8	NC M3	378.09	1.94
9	SW M3	197.32	2.04
10	NC F2	33.4	1.89

SW = Southwest, NC = Northcentral, M=Male, F=Female

Genotypic Diversity:

All four microsatellite loci showed polymorphism across microsatellite loci targeted in the *H. longifilis* individuals. The average allele count per locus (NA) was 2.00 for both populations (Table 3). The number of effective alleles (NE) was higher in the North

Central population (1.65 ± 0.04) compared to the Southwest population (1.44 ± 0.06) (Table 3). The North Central population also exhibited higher levels of heterozygosity, with an observed heterozygosity (H_o) of 0.50 and an expected heterozygosity (H_e) of 0.75 (Table 3). The Southwest population showed lower

heterozygosity ($H_o = 0.21$, $H_e = 0.31$) (Table 3). The relatively large standard deviations for some heterozygosity values are most likely

attributable to small sample size and the limited number of loci analyzed.

Table 3: Allelic variability of *Heterobranchus longifilis*

Sampling Area	Average allele count per locus (NA)	Number of effective alleles (NE)	Heterozygosity (HO)	Heterozygosity (HE)
Southwest	2.00 ± 0.00	1.44 ± 0.06	0.21 ± 0.33	0.31 ± 0.36
North Central	2.00 ± 0.00	1.65 ± 0.04	0.50 ± 0.31	0.75 ± 0.09

Genetic Structure:

Analysis of the genetic divergence between the two populations revealed a fixation index

(F_{ST}) value of 0.225 (Table 4), while the inbreeding coefficient (F_{IS}) was 0.45 (Table 4).

Table 4: Genetic structure of *Heterobranchus longifilis*

FIS	FIT	FST	NM
0.45	0.47	0.225	3.44

Discussion

This study provides a preliminary assessment of the genetic diversity of wild *Heterobranchus longifilis* from southwestern and northcentral zones in Nigeria. The results revealed varying levels of genetic diversity while highlighting potential challenges. The average number of alleles ($N_a = 2.00$) in this study can be compared to moderate allelic richness previously reported in catfish populations in the study of Dalmolin et al., 2019 using microsatellite markers. Also, the number of effective alleles ($NE = 1.44 \pm 0.06$ and 1.65 ± 0.04 in SW and NC, respectively), indicates a low allelic diversity. Similarly, the values of effective number of alleles in this study are comparable to the values obtained in the study of Aliyu and Diyaware (2019), as well as that of Ezilrani and Godwin (2015) for *Clarias gariepinus* respectively. However, the levels of allelic variation in this study indicate that the

wild *Heterobranchus longifilis* from SW and NC had been negatively impacted by several factors, which may include anthropogenic pressures and geographic isolation.

The observed heterozygosity (H_o) in the Southwest population (0.21) was less than expected heterozygosity (H_e), showing a lack of heterozygotes. Also, the studies of Wognin et al., (2020) showed similar genetic structure for six populations of *H. longifilis* in Côte d'Ivoire. Similar patterns of heterozygote deficiency have been reported in catfish genetic studies which are often attributed to non-random mating, subpopulation structure or small effective population sizes (Suleiman et al., 2021). The high inbreeding coefficient ($F_{IS} = 0.45$) observed in this study is expected, due to heterozygote deficits reported in the populations. This is consistent with reports on other catfish populations when gene flow is limited and mating is non-random (Suleiman

et al., 2021). Low sample sizes in genetic studies can also inflate estimates of inbreeding and heterozygote deficiency due to sampling effects (Dalmolin et al., 2019).

Genetic differentiation ($F_{ST} = 0.225$) between sampled populations suggests a moderate level of genetic differentiation which implies that the Southwest and North Central populations are genetically distinct. Genetic differentiation measured by F_{ST} can therefore be used to infer population structure, with values above 0.15 suggesting a heterozygote deficiency within the total sample. This can often be interpreted as moderate differentiation in fish populations (Dalmolin et al., 2019). Similar studies on clariid fishes (Barasa et al., 2014 ; Popoola et al., 2014; Barasa et al., 2017 and Awodiran and Afolabi, 2018) detected substantial population differentiation across sampling locations, reinforcing the notion that geographic separation can structure clariid catfish populations (Suleiman et al., 2021). These findings imply that the two *H. longifilis* populations may serve as distinct genetic units.

Meanwhile, the presence of polymorphic loci and measurable genetic diversity indicates that these wild strains possess the genetic potential for use in breeding programs. Genetic variability is essential for selective breeding and long-term sustainability, as demonstrated in African catfish and other aquaculture species (Dalmolin et al., 2019). The North Central population, with its relatively higher heterozygosity, thus appears to be a more promising candidate for future genetic improvement initiatives.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study suggests that wild *H. longifilis* from North central population possess considerable genetic diversity, while the Southwest strains require urgent conservation intervention and effective management. However, future research should involve increased sampling and marker density to yield more robust estimates of genetic

parameters and to better inform conservation and breeding strategies.

Limitations

The authors acknowledge that a larger sample size and broader number of primers would strengthen the study and allow more statistical conclusions. However, the allocated budget for the study was limited. Despite this, the current design was sufficient to generate preliminary data that support the main conclusions of this study and provide valid foundation for further investigation, even within the practical constraint. In our future study and with additional funding, sampling size will be expanded and more primers for broader genomic coverage will be incorporated.

Consent to publish

All authors hereby declare that we have reviewed and approved the publication.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests, financial or otherwise, that could influence the work presented in this manuscript.

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Author's Contributions

Y.M., N.D.C., O.K.E., G.M.I., and A.G.R. conceptualized the study; O.K.E. designed the methodology, conducted the experiment/laboratory works and wrote the manuscript. Y.M., N.D.C., and G.M.I. conducted fieldwork. Y.M.S., S.A., and I.K. did all technical work including scheduled operational activities for data collection. O.K.E and N.D.C. revised and edited the manuscript. Y.M. proofread it and all authors approved the final draft of the manuscript.

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